

CULTURAL SCIENCE

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TV REPORTING ITS TYPES AND FUNCTIONS

Abstract:

The preparation and transmission of TV reports to the public is the main function of the daily routine, ordinary work activity for all televisions. It is no coincidence that the potential of television is measured by the success of TV reports, which means public interest, a large audience, and high ratings. and a high rating.

Keywords: *TV reporting, types, functions, live, video recording, with commentary, without commentary, interview*

With the establishment of television, a wider, universal audiovisual tool was created. As soon as the information took place, its on-site delivery and perception also paved the way for the widespread introduction of television in industries such as industry, transport, communications, trade and so on. Compared to cinema, TV has much superior features in the display and circulation of cultural values: it gathers a wider audience, can be in everyone's home and demonstrates a colorful selection of programs. Television is the youngest of the synthetic art forms. One of the factors that distinguishes it from the period of its existence is its progress at an unimaginably fast pace of development. The rapid development of technology on television does not go unnoticed in the quality, efficiency and maintainability of the manufactured product. Television has united creative people from various fields of art, engineers and technical personnel.

The 3 main functions of television always maintain their relevance. These are; Enlightenment, information, Entertainment functions.

If a correct and balanced distribution system is established between these three functions, television will not become the object of condemnation of society, but will also demonstrate its civic position rightly. If we pay attention, we can see that developed Western countries are more involved in obtaining, transmitting and disseminating scientific and technical information. In less developed countries, this trend is more evident in information with entertainment and talk show content. As the number of broadcasting materials in the scientific-technical and creative spirit increases, society will perceive this as a need, and the television space will slowly lose its image as an entertainment medium.

The function of television is not only to entertain, it should provide society with information, educate, and raise the level of knowledge. The basis of the idea of enlightenment is the progress of society, the rise of the intellectual level, and the promotion and propagation of scientific achievements. In this regard, television plays an exceptional role.

During the Soviet period, the propaganda task of the media overshadowed its informational task. It is clear that we are talking about ideological propaganda here. More informative, informative-journalistic, artistic and artistic publicistic programs took place in the television space. Among the tasks of informing and

educating, it becomes necessary to put the second more in the foreground, subordinate the first to the second. Because educational work also performs the function of delivering information. In addition to "opening up" and educating the audience, it also provides information transfer to him.

Keeping national, spiritual and universal values alive at the desired level, studying and adequately delivering them to future generations is one of the main tasks facing television.

If we take a look at Azerbaijan television, we can see traces of hardships, hard work, and hard-to-pass paths in our 68-year history. Our television, which is experiencing certain deprivations and absences due to the material and technical base, today has the opportunity to properly use modern information and telecommunication technologies. At the same time, these new opportunities have given important tasks to our television, and have rapidly increased its influence and scope, and at the same time this is continuing.

TV's responsibilities include accurately forming public opinion, controlling the global flow of information, preventing information that contradicts the nation's interests from entering the media, upholding statehood traditions in the global information war, and providing a thorough response to any adversary. In the information society, the formation of a global information environment, a clash of national and global values in this environment, as well as the emergence of new values, is inevitable.

The famous journalist and publisher Joseph Pulitzer evaluated the importance of the media as follows: "Our Republic and its press will rise or fall together". Perfect media means perfect country. Successful media is the media that has the ability and intelligence to understand correctly, the power to write and speak correctly, the power to power. Such media is able to protect public values". It is television, the most influential branch of the media, that is directly obliged to protect national interests. Educating, informing, entertaining society and, most importantly, adequately fulfilling the duty of an "information warrior" in society is the main task of television.

The reporting genre, which belongs to "small-volume audiovisual works" on television, has its own role. TV report is one of the sources of television journalism. The first TV report, which is one of the

operative informative genres of telejournalism, was prepared in Germany in the middle of the 19th century. After Germany, the reportage, which has become widespread in England, France, the USA and Russia, attracts primarily with its synthetic character, promptness, colourfulness and opens up wide creative opportunities for applicants to this genre. For this reason, reportage is the most widespread operative informative genre in modern times. By synthetic we mean mainly that the report includes the characteristics of the interview, news, essay, report, interpretation. Each of the genres mentioned in the reportage has its own place individually. For example, the reporter conducts an interview to find out an expert's opinion on the issue under investigation. Or he uses the features of the essay genre to convey to the viewer the inner world of the interviewer, his social problems. Sometimes he turns to the genre of commentary in order to convey the event to the audience in a clearer and broader sense. As a result of all this, the main purpose of the reportage is to convey information.

TV reporting, its types and functions.

The term reportage is derived from French (reportage) and English (report) and means to inform. The root means to transmit in Latin (reporto).

The reporting genre, which belongs to "small-volume audiovisual works" on television, has its own role. Reportage is one of the sources of television journalism. The reportage genre, which draws its history from literature, was later used in the press and radio. Later, the cinematographer turned to this genre and expanded its scope of activity. The emergence of television accelerated the development of the reporting genre and expanded its scope. At present, analytical, artistic-journalistic and mainly informational reporting genres are used on television.

The reports prepared on television are distinguished by their promptness and wide audience. In newspapers and radio, the report is presented only through words, while in television, the image is also involved.

A television report, as it were, turns the viewer into a participant in the incident. While in newspapers and radio, the journalist prepares the report without anyone's help, in television, this work is created as a product of collective labor. It is qualified for life as a product of the work of a reporter, director, cameraman, sound director, assembler and various other art owners. The role of the director in the creation of the reportage is irreplaceable. Depending on the form and types of TV report, the director's approach to it also changes.

There are two types of presentation of reports on television. This can be a live broadcast or a video recording material. Reports from the scene, such as sports competitions, rallies, parades, government events, and so on, can be broadcast and recorded live through mobile television studios (MTS). In this case, the director must be able to adjust the operation of the cameras from behind the remote control and work at the director's remote control. The preparation of some reports is carried out by the film crew. Here too, the director has certain duties depending on the types of reportage. Such reports are presented to the audience

after editing. Interviews can be annotated and without comments. The reporter can work in the frame or behind the scenes. All these features should be known to the director and be able to build his activities in the style corresponding to the type of reportage.

There are the following forms and types of TV report:

- live-broadcast reporting; incident reporting; staged report; analytical (problematic) reporting; thematic (educational) reporting; special reporting; illustrative reporting; entertaining-reporting; military reporting; sports reporting; production reporting; investigative reporting; commentary-reporting.

TV reporting and its role in television.

Television has three main functions: providing information, educating and entertaining. In all of these areas, the television reporting genre has a place. Of course, first of all, this genre is used in information television. The main part of the types of reportage genre, eventful, analytical, thematic, special reports are precisely informational in nature.

Reports from established (staged), and sports competitions can be attributed to entertainment-type reports. Illustrative, military, production, investigative and reporting-comments, on the other hand, are distinguished by more educational overtones. It is impossible to imagine modern television separately from the reportage genre.

4 points of view to the TV reporting.

The prepared report can be approached from four points of view.

- 1) The material prepared from the scene of the incident is presented according to the principle of one reportage and one information. The interviewees share their views on the main issue. And their thoughts are aimed only at revealing the information presented, not going beyond the margins.

This approach allows the reporter to quickly prepare the report and present it in the news release.

- 2) In this case, the audience is presented with a report and some information. Here the interviewees approach the issue from their own point of view. As a result, various, sometimes different ideas are formed. The reporter must be able to logically put these ideas together and present them to the audience. Unlike the first, this approach makes the material richer, separate approaches to the issue add analytical features. This, in turn, requires higher professionalism from the journalist.

- 3) Another method of presentation is presented by the principle of one report-one expert-many data. In this interview, all issues are told in the language of one person-the hero. It is important to choose the hero. It can be either a strong specialist, a person with great experience in this field, or someone who has complete information about the issue.

- 4) Finally the last point of view. One report-many experts-many information. In such a report, the reporter works with many interviewees and collects a lot of information. Since the information in these reports is abundant and sometimes contradictory, it requires skill and mastery from the author. Directing all information, facts, ideas into a single course is its main goal. Such

type of reportage is mainly used in travel, adventure programs.

CONCLUSION

The important issues for telereporting are not only the observations and thoughts of the reporter, but mainly the attitude of the witnesses to the fact and the incident. The main issue for the reporter is not only what to entertain, but also how to present the event. There is no uninteresting topic. Behind any topic is the interest of the audience. Therefore, we repeat once again, there is no uninteresting topic, there is an uninteresting presentation. If the reporter has set himself the goal of reporting from any event, he should first of all take into account the interest of the audience, make the most of "empathy" (empathy is a Greek word meaning "to share in suffering"). [31] Therefore, the most important issue for the report is the selection of the topic and its successful delivery to the audience. Of course, a professional TV journalist can work on any socio-political or social topic experienced in society as a report and present it to the general public. However, in this case, the journalist must answer the main question: "What will the plot that I will prepare give the audience something new?". Only after finding the answer to that question and determining for himself the social significance and relevance of the topic to be studied, the TV journalist can decide to prepare a report. In other words the topic chosen for the report should be of greater interest to the audience, focus directly on solving the problem and reflect the views of specialists who have great influence in the public sphere, especially independent experts. Otherwise, the report will be received unsuccessfully and will have no effect. Thus, public importance for reporting is the point that precedes promptness.

This is how professional TV journalists group other principles that are important for reporting:

- The news selected for the report should have informative value and touch on the main issues that make the viewer think and worry. The viewer should determine his future activity and lifestyle by watching this news.

- The theme of the TV report should have the power to bring prestige to the TV journalist, the reporter to the TV channel represented by these people, and even to the ordinary viewer who will later share this news with the public and relatives, and attract attention with its interesting and unusual.

- The subject of the report should not cause mental shock, tension, fear and discouragement in people, but, on the contrary, should evoke feelings of patriotism, compassion and humanity in the viewer.

- The topic of the interview should be not only close, but also native to a larger audience. The audience should feel closely the material or the problem raised in the plot, and should wish to participate in that issue.

- The topic of the interview should be distinguished by its relevance and promptness, as well as aesthetic value.

Identification of an interesting idea or a topic of social significance is 30-40 percent of the work. Now it remains to realize in reality that subject that lives in fantasies. After the topic of the TV report is chosen,

the TV journalist should think about preparing it, turn on his fantasy, connections. In this case, following some advice will benefit the general cause.

The main creative principles that make TV reporting interesting are as follows:

- Writing sentences in short and laconic form;
- Thoughtful, emotional reading of the text;
- Maximum use of moving frames;
- Use of ambient sound as much as possible, but on the spot.

It should be noted that, TV report is not a presentation of the event in a slow form, with long thoughts. In order to tell the audience the essence of the event, a reporter or journalist must develop a dynamic reading style, and demonstrate acting qualities, both when reading a text and in "Stand-Up", in dialogues and monologues. He should take full advantage of the principle of operatively replacing each other, characteristic of a newsreel. The mentioned principles directly affect the expressiveness of the material. Let's not forget that the TV journalist has the opportunity to address the audience only once. Therefore, the plots should be written so clearly and transmitted to the audience that everyone sitting in front of the screen can perceive the TV report at first sight. It is for this reason that a clear, precise style and logical assembly are important requirements for telereporting.

Each plot has a certain tempo rhythm corresponding to the theme. Therefore, when determining the topic of the TV report, the behind-the-scenes text should be read in accordance with that temporality, in other words, the intonation of the plot should be adjusted to its theme. Only in this case, the viewer will be able to listen carefully to the plot and grasp the general theme, getting into the course of the event.

One of the important issues is the correct presentation of sound and image in TV reporting. The question is: Should the voice come first in the plot or the description?. Of course: description. Whether it is a plot or a documentary, in television creativity, the description is always presented first. And then the word explains that description. Therefore, if we want the telereporting to be more successful, the sound sequence and image should complement the plot's content. Otherwise, the viewer will either not understand what we mean, or there will be serious difficulties with perception.

When preparing a TV report, it is necessary to touch on the moments that make the public think and worry, to approach this topic from a completely different position. The main goal facing the reporter is not only to bring the event and what is visible at first glance to the public. A reporter who is more interested in behind-the-scenes moments should try to determine the causes of the event, future complications and future development directions of the process, as well as reveal the moments that no one has seen. This is real professionalism.

As in all areas of art, it is important to master all the little things of this genre in order to further delve into the genre of TV reporting. The article clearly

studies television reporting, its types and functions carried by it, indicating with accuracy.

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